

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND SEDENTARY BEHAVIOR AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS: AN IPAQ-BASED CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Physical inactivity is a major modifiable risk factor for non-communicable diseases. Medical students, despite their future role as health promoters, are frequently reported to have insufficient physical activity and high sedentary behavior. This study aimed to assess physical activity levels, sedentary time, and gender differences among medical students using the International Physical Activity Questionnaire Short Form (IPAQ-SF). A cross-sectional study was conducted among 150 undergraduate medical students in 2025. Physical activity was assessed using the IPAQ-SF and expressed as metabolic equivalent task minutes per week (MET-min/week). Participants were categorized into low, moderate, and high physical activity groups according to established IPAQ criteria. Gender differences were analyzed using Welch's t-test and chi-square tests.

Keywords: physical activity; IPAQ; sedentary behavior; medical students; public health

Introduction. Insufficient physical activity is a leading modifiable determinant of non-communicable diseases, including cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and selected cancers [1,2-6]. In response, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that adults engage in at least 150–300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity or 75–150 minutes of vigorous-intensity activity per week, together with muscle-strengthening activities on two or more days per week [3,2]. Medical students represent a key population in preventive health. As future physicians, they are expected to counsel patients on lifestyle modification and disease prevention. However, growing evidence indicates that medical students themselves frequently fail to meet recommended physical activity thresholds and spend prolonged periods in sedentary behavior due to academic workload, stress, and time constraints [4-7,11,13]. Gender disparities have been consistently reported, with female medical students exhibiting lower levels of physical activity than males across different regions and cultural settings [8-12]. The International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) is widely used in population-based studies and has demonstrated acceptable reliability and validity in young adult populations [13,14,3,5]. The short form (IPAQ-SF) allows standardized assessment of weekly physical activity volume using metabolic equivalent task units (METs), facilitating international comparison. This study aimed to assess physical activity levels, sedentary behavior, and perceived barriers among medical students using the IPAQ-SF, with a particular focus on statistically significant gender differences.

Purpose. Explanatory work to identify and define the lack of physical activity among the population, which is a consequence of the occurrence of various types of diseases.

Material and methods. A cross-sectional study was conducted during the 2025 academic year among

undergraduate medical students. A total of 150 students participated voluntarily. The mean age was 20.5 ± 2.1 years. Females accounted for 65.3% ($n = 98$) and males for 34.7% ($n = 52$). The mean body mass index (BMI) was 22.4 ± 3.8 kg/m². Physical activity was assessed using the IPAQ Short Form, which captures frequency and duration of walking, moderate-intensity activity, and vigorous-intensity activity during the previous seven days. Weekly physical activity volume was calculated in MET-min/week using standard coefficients: walking = 3.3 METs, moderate activity = 4.0 METs, vigorous activity = 8.0 METs. Sedentary behavior was assessed as self-reported average daily sitting time (hours/day). Participants also reported perceived barriers to regular physical activity. Continuous variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Gender differences in physical activity volume were evaluated using Welch's t-test. Associations between gender and physical activity categories were assessed using chi-square tests. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$. Participants were classified into three categories: •low physical activity (< 600 MET-min/week), •moderate physical activity (600–3000 MET-min/week), •high physical activity (> 3000 MET-min/week).

Results and discussion. According to tab.1, overall, 42.0% of students were classified as having low physical activity, 45.3% moderate activity, and only 12.7% high activity. According to tab.2, male students demonstrated significantly higher weekly physical activity compared with female students (2350 ± 1410 vs. 1450 ± 920 MET-min/week, $p < 0.001$). A significant association between gender and physical activity category was observed, with low physical activity being more prevalent among females ($p = 0.002$). Mean daily sitting time was 7.2 hours. The most frequently reported barriers were lack of time (68%) and post-class

fatigue (52%). This study demonstrates a high prevalence of insufficient physical activity and sedentary behavior among medical students. More than 40% of participants did not meet minimum WHO physical activity recommendations, consistent with findings from multiple international studies. A key finding is the pronounced and statistically significant gender disparity in

physical activity, with female students exhibiting substantially lower weekly activity levels. Similar patterns have been reported in IPAQ-based studies across Europe, the Middle East, and South America, suggesting that this phenomenon is widespread and multifactorial.

Table 1.

Participant characteristics	
Characteristic	Value
Sample size	150
Age (years), mean \pm SD	20.5 \pm 2.1
Female, n (%)	98 (65.3)
Male, n (%)	52 (34.7)
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	22.4 \pm 3.8

Table 2.

Physical activity categories according to IPAQ-SF		
Category	N	%
Low	63	42.0
Moderate	68	45.3
High	19	12.7

Figure. Weekly physical activity volume by gender (mean \pm SD)

Results. The observed sedentary time exceeding seven hours per day is clinically relevant. Evidence increasingly indicates that prolonged sitting independently contributes to cardiometabolic risk, even among physically active individuals. WHO guidelines therefore emphasize both increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary behavior. Time constraints and academic fatigue were the dominant barriers reported, highlighting the need for institutional approaches rather than relying solely on individual motivation. Embedding physical activity promotion within medical curricula and providing accessible opportunities for exercise may improve adherence and foster long-term healthy behaviors among future physicians.

References

1. Alzahrani HA, Ahmad MT, Algarni AS, et al. Physical activity levels among medical students. *Med Teach*. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09581596.2025.2472847>
2. Bull FC, Al-Ansari SS, Biddle S, et al. World Health Organization 2020 guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. *Br J Sports Med*. 2020;54:1451–1462. <https://bjsm.bmj.com/content/54/24/1451>
3. Craig CL, Marshall AL, Sjöström M, et al. International Physical Activity Questionnaire: reliability and validity. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*. 2003;35:1381–1395.

<https://doi.org/10.1249/01.MSS.0000078924.61453.FB>

4. Guthold R, Stevens GA, Riley LM, Bull FC. Worldwide trends in insufficient physical activity. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2018;6:e1077–e1086. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30357-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30357-7)

5. IPAQ Research Committee. Guidelines for Data Processing and Analysis of the International Physical Activity Questionnaire. <https://sites.google.com/view/ipaq/home>

6. Lee IM, Shiroma EJ, Lobelo F, et al. Effect of physical inactivity on major non-communicable diseases worldwide. *Lancet*. 2012;380:219–229. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)61031-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61031-9)

7. Mohamed S, Muhammad SA, Mohamed AA, et al. Physical activity promotes well-being: medical students' engagement and perspective. *Ann Med Surg*. 2025;87:76–84. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MS9.0000000000002808>

8. Owen N, Healy GN, Matthews CE, Dunstan DW. Too much sitting. *Exerc Sport Sci Rev*. 2010;38:105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JES.0b013e3181e373a2>

9. Papathanasiou G, Georgoudis G, Papandreou M, et al. Reliability of the short IPAQ in young adults.

Hellenic J Cardiol. 2009;50:283–294.

https://www.hellenicjcardiol.org/archive/full_text/2009/4/2009_4_283.pdf

10. Recker AJ, Sugimoto SF, Halvorson EE, Skelton JA. Knowledge and habits of exercise in medical students. *Am J Lifestyle Med*. 2021;15:214–219. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559827620963884>

11. Rippe JM. Lifestyle medicine: the health promoting power of daily habits. *Am J Lifestyle Med*. 2019;13:109–112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559827619832931>

12. Schlickmann DW, Kock KS. Physical activity knowledge of medical students. *J Lifestyle Med*. 2022;12:47–55. <https://doi.org/10.15280/jlm.2022.12.1.47>

13. Trilk JL, Phillips EM. Exercise is medicine in medical education. *Sports Med Health Sci*. 2019. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666337619300025>

14. World Health Organization. WHO Guidelines on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour. 2020. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240015128>